

SPORTS MASSAGE

Sirojev Shoxrux

Asia International University
Physical culture chair manager

Email: sirojevshoxruxfayzullougli@oxu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10896656>

Anatasia

Massage is believed to have a history of 5,000 years. In Hindi, the words "masser", Arabic "disorder", Hebrew "mashesh", Greek "massein" mean to stroke, knead. The 19th century saw a high growth in the number of doctors interested in massage. During this period, the Swede Peter Henre Ling (1778-1839) took his place in history as the first person to scientifically establish the massage technique and created the scientific foundations of today's Swedish massage. Sports massage, on the other hand, is the manipulation of techniques associated with classical massage to improve the athlete's health and general condition and to enhance or maintain athletic performance. From another point of view, this is a classic massage method used to increase the athlete's motivation, support his special warm-up before the general warm-up, and accelerate his recovery after training. The Swedish Peter Henri Ling and later A. Hoffa developed the basis of classical massage. In his book published in 1893, he divided massage manipulation into five: efflorage, petrissage, friction, tapotement, and vibration. These techniques are currently being taught as a course at the Physiotherapy Department of Hacettepe University. Today, sports massage has been formalized in many clubs and has become a very important auxiliary element used as treatment methods in addition to sports performance.

Keywords; Sports massage, massage, sports

History and massage

Massage is believed to have a history of 5,000 years. In Hindi, the words "masser", Arabic "disorder", Hebrew "mashesh", Greek "massein" mean stroking, kneading. In those centuries, massage movements were used in a complex, unsystematic and unknown manner, and could only have a psychological effect on the patient. I believe that massage, which is actually a touch technique, is associated with Adam and the Prophet Muhammad. Eve returns. Because we are creatures with the human instinct to experience what we see by touching it. Our sense of touch is perhaps the most basic form of perception. A baby in the womb receives its first impressions through touch. Maybe that's why touch is reassuring and comforting. Massage can be defined as a tendency to exert physiological and psychological effects on the body through systematic manipulations through mechanical stimulation of soft tissues. Classical massage manipulation consists of five parts: stroking (euphoria), kneading (petrissage), friction, tapotement and vibration. These are effloration (stroking), friction (circular friction), petrissage (kneading), compression (pressure), percussion (impact blows), vibration (vibration) and again effloration. The reassurance and peace provided by touch has

been effective in health care applications over time. Systematic and rhythmic methods of treatment, that is, manipulations, appeared.

Sports massage

Sports massage is a contribution to a person's preparation and performance for competition. sports massage is a type of massage that is effective in the physical and physiological development of an athlete. The growing interest in massage in various sports and physical activity in developing countries has contributed to the development of the field of sports massage, and has greatly contributed to the professional formation of sports massage therapists and massage therapists. Sports massage is also used as a treatment method for athletes due to sports injuries. Applying sports massage before a competition or training session is a passive warm-up in preparation for an active warm-up. Any disruptions that may occur between competitions or the use of manipulations that must be performed locally. Especially the post-race massage is very effective. Because post-competition massage not only contributes to the elimination of waste products from the body, but also helps a person to quickly prepare and relax for the next training or competition.

The main purpose of sports massage: The goal is to passively support the athlete's warm-up before training or competition, to prepare him for the next training session faster and more rested after the competition, to support the treatment of injuries that may occur as a result of manipulations. is to support and contribute to its operation. There are many definitions of sports massage. If we consider some of them, Sports massage is the science of using classical massage manipulations to make the athlete feel good, protect his health and improve his performance. sports massage is a massage that is performed to increase the strength of athletes and ensure that they rest faster. Sports massage is the use of classical massage and methods related to classical massage to improve the health and general condition of the athlete and increase sports performance. Sports massage is a classic massage that is performed to increase the motivation of the athlete, support the warm-up and facilitate recovery after training. Thanks to sports massage, the feeling of pain in nerves and muscles is reduce

Why sports massage?

- 1) To improve sports performance and give the athlete a better start before the competition.
- 2) Provide short rest (recovery) before training and competition.
- 3) To have a positive effect on the athlete's psychology, which affects success.
- 4) prevent injuries and ensure return to sports as soon as possible.

Sports massage is divided into 3 types

These are:

1. Massage, training (activity) before the competition
2. Break or break (between activities) massage
3. Massage after competition, training (activity).

Massage before competition or training (activity).

This is a pre-competition, pre-training (activity) massage. Sometimes a general massage is done the day before the competition, and the massage given to the athlete for psychological relaxation and rest with good sleep is also partially considered as a pre-competition massage. But it is mainly used for warming up and motivation before training. It includes passive heating methods used before active heating. It is done within 4 hours before the activity. Ideal - done 30-45 minutes before. The duration of the massage should not exceed

5-20 minutes. The large muscle groups to be used during the activity should be targeted locally. Stimulating the muscles before the competition helps to increase flexibility. In order to accelerate blood circulation, muscle pumping, direct pressure, isolation, mobilization and stretching methods are used. Painful methods are never used. Although light and impressive techniques are preferred, they should be done smoothly and quickly. In this period, motivational work is carried out together with the use of massage.

Break or break (between activities) massage

This is a massage between competitions or training. It is useful for athletes who participate in one or more competitions in a short period of time in terms of recovery and maintaining performance. This is usually done with very short breaks, using no oil or very little lubricant (depending on the sport). Massage 10-15 minutes. It should last (usually 10 minutes) and should not be painful. Techniques should be used sequentially. Priority muscle groups should be targeted and techniques should be used in these areas. It really shouldn't be tiring. If lotion is to be used, consideration should be given to the lotions used, taking into account whether the weather conditions are hot or cold.

Massage (activity) after competition or training.

This is a massage after competition and training (activity). It accelerates physical, physiological and spiritual recovery. Its purpose is; With sufficient doses of efflorescence and petrissage applied to the body in the direction of the heart, the lymphatic and venous systems are stimulated and blood circulation is activated. With the revitalization of the flow in the veins, the fluid exchange in the tissues is accelerated, the tissues can receive more nutrients and oxygen; Metabolic waste can be removed faster. This should be done within 4 hours after the activity. 20 minutes if done during the cooling period. It should not pass. If it needs to be done for relaxation or psychological purposes, it can last up to 1 hour. Muscle relaxation helps to quickly return to pre-activity physiological data. In addition, injury prevention is an important part of taking precautions for potential or already occurring injuries. kneading, positional relaxation, joint mobilization and stretching, should be used. It should never be used if hypothermia or hyperthermia is suspected. In problematic situations, you should not do this, you should contact the first aid and health department.

Summary

Today, many studies have shown that sports massage has a positive and supportive effect on athletes psychologically and physiologically. In addition, the presence of a masseuse or masseuse in mass and mass sports (football) was formalized. Sports massage, performed as a passive warm-up before an active warm-up, has the properties to counteract injuries that may occur during an active warm-up, support muscle stretching, and increase blood circulation. In most sports, injuries are usually based on muscle factors. In sports massage, the muscles work fully. Stimulating techniques are used before the competition. In particular, techniques are used for which muscle group the competitions are aimed at. Stimulating methods should be avoided at the end of the competition. Because the muscle is tired. Sports massage is a manual therapy that, in addition to supporting a comprehensive active warm-up, contributes to the prevention of injuries and injuries that may occur during work.

References:

- 1.Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND WORKING METHODS OF COACHES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 50–60.
- 2.Shoxrux, S. (2023). VOLEYBOLDA OTISH TEZLIGI TUSHUNCHASI VA AHAMIYATI. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 1(11), 913-917.
- 3.Sirojev, S. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 187-191.
- 4.Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORTS AND LOGIC. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 97–106.
- 5.Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). APPLICATIONS OF SPORT PSYCHOLOGY IN THE WORLD. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 107–120.
6. Sirojev, S. (2023). TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND PHILOSOPHY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 235–243.
- 7.Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF MUTUAL RESPECT AND KINDNESS IN SPORTS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 215–225.
- 8.Sirojev, S. (2024). EFFECTS OF SOCIAL PHOBIA ON SPORTS. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 318–326.
- 9.Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). STUDYING SPORTS PSYCHOLOGY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 176–188.
- 10.Sirojev , S. (2024). EFFECTS OF WARM-UP AND STRETCHING EXERCISES ON PROPRIOCEPTION AND BALANCE. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 353–361.
- 11.Rahmonova, S. (2023). YUKSAK MA'NAVİYATLÍ AVLOD-UCHINCHÍ RENESSANS BUNYODKORLARI. Наука и технология в современном мире, 2(3), 76-79.
- 12.Rahmonova, S. (2023). DYNAMICS AND MAIN DIRECTIONS OF SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN UZBEKISTAN. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 850-854.
- 13.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). PHYSIOLOGICAL REACTIONS TO INTERNAL LOAD STUDY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-07>
- 14.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS PEDAGOGY BASED ON PSYCHOMOTOR AND DEVELOPMENT THEORIES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-05>
- 15.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS, CULTURE AND SOCIETY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 152–163. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-17>
- 16.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). FOCUS ON AEROBIC (LI) TYPE OF MOTOR ACTIVITY BASED ON FITNESS PROGRAMS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 81–90.
- 17.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). METHODS OF ORGANIZING NON-TRADITIONAL FITNESS CLASSES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-09>
- 18.Yarasheva Dilnoza Ismail Qizi. (2023). TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS IN SPORTS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(10), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue10-16>

19.Yarashova, D. (2023). THE IMPACT OF PLAYING SPORTS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 230–234. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24325>

20.Ярашева, Д. (2023, April). ФИТНЕС КАК ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies (Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 278-283)*.

